

Synthesis, Partition coefficient and antibacterial activity of 3'-aryl-6'-phenyl(substituted)-*cis*-5'*a*,6'-dihydrospiro[3*H*-indole- 3,4'-thiazolo(5',1'-*c*)-isoxazolo-2-(1*H*)-ones]

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Abstract : Condensation of isatin with primary aryl amines gave a series of Schiff bases (1) which on reaction with thioglycolic acid in 1,4-dioxane afforded the corresponding thiazolidones (2). Compound 2 on condensation with substituted benzaldehydes in anhydrous sodium acetate furnished 3-aryl-5'-phenyl(substituted)spiro[3*H*-indole-3,2'-thiazolidines]-2-(1*H*), 4'(5'*H*)-diones (3). The latter on reaction with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in anhydrous sodium acetate gave the title compounds (4). The structures have been established on the basis of spectral data. The Partition coefficient for *n*-octanol/water solvent system and *in vitro* antibacterial activity of this compounds have been evaluated.

Keywords : Schiff base, Partition coefficient, log *p*.

Isatinoid derivatives^{1,2}, as well as different heterocyclic systems containing thiazole and isoxazole ring³⁻⁶ possess potent biological activities. In continuation of our earlier work on isatins, it was thought worthwhile of incorporating these units with a hope to develop a series of spiro nitrogen bridge isatinoid derivatives. We, report herein, the synthesis of 3'-arylspro [3*H*-indole-3,2'-thiazolidine]-2-(1*H*),4'-(5'*H*)-diones, their conversion to 3-aryl-5'-phenyl(substituted)-spiro[3*H*-indole-3,2'-thiazolidine]-2-(1*H*),4'-(5'*H*)-diones and further to the title compounds and determination of their Partition coefficient for *n*-octanol/water solvent system and possible antibacterial activity.

Results and discussion

Isatin on condensation with primary aryl amines gave Schiff bases (1a-g) which on reaction with thioglycolic acid in 1,4-dioxane furnished 3'-arylspro[3*H*-indole-3,2'-thiazolidine]-2-(1*H*),4'-(5'*H*)-diones (2a-g). The latter on reaction with substituted benzaldehydes in anhydrous sodium acetate afforded 3-aryl-5'-phenyl(substituted) spiro[3*H*-indole-3,2'-thiazolidine]-2-(1*H*),4'-(5'*H*)diones (3a₁-g₁, a₂-g₂, a₃-g₃, a₄-g₄, a₅-g₅) which, in turn, reacted with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in anhydrous sodium acetate to furnish 3'-aryl-6'-phenyl(substituted)-*cis*-5'*a*,6'-dihydrospiro-[3*H*-indole-3,4'-thiazolo(5',1'-*c*)-isoxazolo-2-(1*H*)-ones] (4a₁-g₁, a₂-g₂, a₃-g₃, a₄-g₄, a₅-g₅).

The Partition coefficient of selected title compounds was performed by classical shake flask method⁷ using *n*-octanol and aqueous phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), the results of which are presented in Table 1. All the compounds tested were thought to be ideal drug candidates, as it was suggested that an ideal drug candidate should have log *p* value in the range of 1 to 2.

Table 1. log *p* value

Compd.	log <i>p</i>
4a ₂	1.21
a ₅	1.44
b ₂	1.08
b ₅	1.20
c ₂	1.39
c ₄	1.28
d ₂	1.42
d ₃	1.58
e ₂	1.13
e ₄	1.29
f ₂	1.42
f ₅	1.22
g ₂	1.57
g ₅	1.52

The antibacterial activity of the title compounds were determined by agar cup plate method⁸, the results of which

are presented in Table 2. Among the compounds 4b₂, b₃, b₅, c₄, c₅, d₂ and d₄, were found to be most active against all the microbes tested. However, all the test compounds were less active in comparison to ampicillin trihydrate (standard drug)

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and were uncorrected. Purity of the compounds were checked by TLC. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Jasco FTIR 410 spectrophotometer (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) on a Bruker DPX 300-MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal reference (chemical shifts in δ ppm). Mass spectra were scanned on a Jeol JSM-600 spectrometer operating at 70 eV. C, H and N analyses were carried out on a Euro EA (Italy) analyzer

Schiff bases (1) were prepared following the reported method⁹

3'-Arylspiro[3H-indole-3,2'-thiazolidine]-2-(1H),4'-(5'-H)-diones (2) : An equimolar mixture of compound 1 (0.001 mol) and thioglycolic acid (0.001 mol, 0.122 g) in 1,4-dioxane (50 ml) was refluxed for 10–12 h. The excess solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the liquified residue was poured into ice-cold water. The solid thus obtained was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallized from ethanol. **2a** (60%); m.p. 158°; ν_{\max} 3361 (NH), 3045 (CH-arom.), 1736 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 3.52 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.78–7.46 (9H, m, ArH), 8.74 (1H, s, NH).

Table 2. Antibacterial activity data (zone of inhibition^a) of the title compounds in the concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

Compd	S a	A p	E c	K a
4a ₁	12	13	14	14
a ₂	16	14	15	14
a ₃	13	14	14	13
a ₄	13	13	11	12
a ₅	12	11	12	10
b ₁	14	14	13	14
b ₂	19	20	19	20
b ₃	23	24	24	23
b ₄	17	18	18	17
b ₅	21	21	20	21
c ₁	13	10	11	12
c ₂	18	19	18	18
c ₃	17	18	19	18
c ₄	21	20	21	21
c ₅	22	23	21	22
d ₁	15	15	15	15
d ₂	21	19	20	20
d ₃	17	14	15	13
d ₄	20	20	19	19
d ₅	18	19	19	17
e ₁	16	17	17	17
e ₂	12	12	11	12
e ₃	18	18	18	18
e ₄	15	12	12	11
e ₅	14	14	15	14
f ₁	15	16	16	15
f ₂	13	13	13	12
f ₃	15	15	15	15
f ₄	15	14	14	13
f ₅	12	13	14	14
g ₁	15	14	15	14
g ₂	14	14	13	14
g ₃	18	18	18	17
g ₄	18	17	18	17
g ₅	17	17	18	16
Ampicillin trihydrate		30	32	31
DMSO	00	00	00	00

^aDiameter of the hole is 6 mm. S a = *Staphylococcus aureus*, A p = *Actinomyces pyogenus*, E c = *Escherichia coli*, K a = *Klebsiella aerogenus*

Note

3-Aryl-5'-phenyl(substituted)spiro[3H-indole-3,2'-thiazolidine]-2-(1H),4'-(5'-H)-diones (**3**) : An equimolar mixture of compound **2** (0.001 mol), substituted benzaldehydes (0.001 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.001 mol, 0.082 g) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated and poured into ice-cold water. The solid thus separated, was filtered, washed with water and crystallized from glacial acetic acid : **3a₂** (71%); m.p. 212°; ν_{max} 3447 (NH), 3026 (CH-arom.), 1722 (C=O), 1540 (asym. NO₂), 1354 cm⁻¹ (sym. NO₂); δ 6.12 (1H, s, CH), 6.76–7.45 (13H, m, ArH), 8.81 (1H, s, NH).

3'-Aryl-6'-phenyl(substituted)-cis-5'a,6'-dihydrospiro[3H-indole-3,4'-thiazolo(5',1'-c)-isoxazolo-2-(1H)-ones] (**4**) : An equimolar mixture of compound **3** (0.001 mol) in ethanol (20 ml), anhydrous sodium acetate (0.001 mol, 0.082 g) in minimum amount of glacial acetic acid and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.001 mol, 0.069 g) was refluxed for 7–8 h. The solid thus separated, was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and crystallized from ethanol : **4a₃** (65%); m.p. 196°; δ 3.70 (1H, d, CH), 4.32 (1H, d, CH), 6.72–7.44 (13H, m, ArH), 8.60 (1H, s, NH); **4a₅** (51%); m.p. 118° (Found : C, 66.78; H, 4.32; N, 10.57. C₂₃H₁₇N₃O₃S calcd. for : C, 66.49; H, 4.12; N, 10.11%); ν_{max} 3402 (NH), 3078 (CH-arom.), 1742 (C=O), 1624 (C=N), 1328 cm⁻¹ (C–O–N); δ 3.70 (1H, d, CH), 4.30 (1H,

d, CH), 6.74–7.43 (13H, m, ArH), 8.87 (1H, s, NH); **4c₅** (56%); m.p. 106°; m/z 449 (M⁺), 74 (base peak)

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